

New Synthetic Analogues of Isotocin, Mesotocin, Arginine and Lysine Vasotocin

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Four new synthetic analogues of isotocin, mesotocin, arginine vasotocin, and lysine vasotocin containing 4-fluoro proline in position 7 has been synthesized.

THE chemical structure of the two posterior pituitary hormones, oxytocin and vasopressin, are completely established^{1,2}, and they have been synthesized^{3, 5}. Structure activity relationship of synthetic variation of oxytocin and vasopressin has held an important place in pharmaceutical chemistry, pharmacology, and biochemistry⁶⁻¹².

For this purpose four new synthetic analogues of isotocin (4-Ser-8 Ileu-oxytocin), mesotocin (8-Ileu oxytocin), arginine vasotocin (3-Ileu-arginine vasopressin) and lysine vasotocin (3-Ileu-lysine vasopressin) containing fluoro proline in positions 7 has been synthesized. Fluoro proline was used because of the unusual and often unexpected properties¹³ which the fluorine atom gives to the molecule, also some fluorinated amino acid

possess outstanding effectiveness as competitive inhibitors¹⁴. The nona peptides were prepared stepwise using the *p*-nitrophenyl-ester method by scheme 1 (for synthesis of isotocin and mesotocin), and by scheme 2 (for synthesis of arginine, and lysine vasotocin). The structure of the nona peptides (XIV, XV, XVI, XVII) was confirmed by its analytical data, and by amino acid analysis after its hydrolysis with 6*N* HCl at 110° for about 22 hr. Final removal of protecting groups from the nona peptides amide was carried out at 0° for 30 min. in HF¹⁵, the compound (100 mg) was dissolved in trifluoro acetic acid (0.5 ml) together with anisole (0.08 ml) before treatment with HF (5 ml.). After the reaction, HF was removed under vacuum, and the reaction product was taken up into 100 ml of water. The solution was adjusted to pH 6.7 with ammonia,

Scheme 1 for synthesis of isotocin and mesotocin.

Scheme 2 for synthesis of arginine and lysine vasotocin.

and carbon dioxide-free air was bubbled through the solution for about 2 hr, and some biological testing are under consideration.

Experimental

The time allowed for the completion of the reaction and the purity of the prepared compounds was controlled by means of thin layer chromatography (T.L.C.) using freshly prepared solvent (butanol : water : acetic acid 62:26:12). The N-benzyloxycarbonyl amino acids and peptides were detected by ninhydrin spray on chromatograms after treating with hydrogen bromide in acetic acid at room temperature (20°) for 1 hr. Melting points were uncorrected.

General method for preparation of peptides : To N-benzyloxycarbonyl-peptide amide^{16,17} (1 mol) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (1.8 ml). After being allowed to stand for one hour at room temperature dry ether (100 ml) was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was washed with ether (10 ml) and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the least amount of dimethyl formamide and triethylamine (1 mol) was added, followed by benzyloxycarbonyl amino acid *p*-nitro phenylester^{18,19} (1 mol). After being left for 18 hr at room temperature the solid mass was treated with ethyl acetate (75 ml), filtered, washed with 2*N* HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, water, ether, and then recrystallized from ethyl acetate.

Z-L-Pro(4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (I) : m.p. 115°-16° ; R_F 0.54, [α]_D²⁰ = -37° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found C, 57.72 ; H, 6.59 ; N, 12.78 ; F, 4.30 ; C₂₁H₂₉N₄O₄ FS, requires C, 57.80 ; H, 6.50 ; N, 12.84 ; F, 4.35%).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (II) : m. p. 130°-31° ; R_F 0.53 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -41° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found C, 58.95 ; H, 6.45 ; N, 11.02 ; F, 2.98 ; C₃₁H₄₁N₆O₅FS, requires C, 59.02 ; H, 6.50 ; N, 11.11 ; F, 3.01%).

Z-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (III) : m. p. 145°-47° ; R_F 0.62 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -47° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 56.38 ; H, 6.27 ; N, 13.05 ; F, 2.49 ; C₃₃H₄₇N₄O₇FS, requires C, 56.45 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 13.17 ; F, 2.55%).

Z-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (IV) : m.p. 160°-62° ; R_F 0.66 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -51° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 55.39 ; H, 6.21 ; N, 14.31 ; F, 2.08 ; C₄₀H₆₅N₉O₉FS, requires C, 55.45 ; H, 6.30 ; N, 14.44 ; F, 2.17%).

Z-L-Ser-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (V) : m. p. 173°-75° ; R_F 0.65 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -53° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 58.22 ; H, 6.73 ; N, 14.35 ; F, 2.50 ; C₃₃H₅₂N₈O₉FS, requires C, 58.08 ; H, 6.62 ; N, 14.26 ; F, 2.42%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (VI) : m. p. 173°-75° ; R_F 0.7 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -61° (C=1, in D. M. F.) Found : C, 55.83 ; H, 6.52 ; N, 14.02 ; F, 1.83 ; C₄₆H₆₆N₁₀O₁₀ FS, requires C, 55.98 ; H, 6.69 ; N, 14.20 ; F, 1.92%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Ser-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (VII) : m. p. 185°-87° ; R_F 0.69 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -57° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 58.93 ; H, 7.13 ; N, 14.15 ; F, 2.22 ; C₄₄H₆₃N₉O₁₀FS, requires C, 58.80 ; H, 7.01 ; N, 14.03 ; F, 2.11%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Arg (NO₂)-Gly NH₂ (VIII) : m.p. 220°-22° ; R_F 0.6 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -59° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 51.29 ; H, 6.11 ; N, 18.33 ; F, 1.88 ; C₄₆H₆₅N₁₄O₁₃ FS ; requires C, 51.44 ; H, 6.05 ; N, 18.26 ; F, 1.79%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Lys (Tos)-Gly NH₂ (IX) : m.p. 230°-33° ; R_F 0.58 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -61° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 55.19 ; H, 6.41 ; N, 13.44 ; F, 1.77 ; C₅₃H₇₃N₁₁O₁₃S₂F, requires C, 55.06 ; H, 6.32 ; N, 13.33 ; F, 1.64%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (X) : m.p. 190°-92° ; R_F 0.77 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -70° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 58.80 ; H, 6.12 ; N, 11.89 ; F, 1.38 ; C₆₃H₈₁N₁₁O₁₄ FS, requires C, 58.92 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 12.00 ; F, 1.48%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Ser-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (XI) : m. p. 210°-12° ; R_F 0.7 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -61° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 59.85 ; H, 6.65 ; N, 13.24 ; F, 1.82 ; C₅₈H₇₂N₁₀O₁₂ FS, requires C, 59.94 ; H, 6.78 ; N, 13.19 ; F, 1.78%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Arg (NO₂)-Gly NH₂ (XII): m. p. 240°-41°, R_F 0.65; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -70^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found: C, 53.58; H, 5.83; N, 16.80; F, 1.60; C₆₅H₇₄N₁₅O₁₈FS, requires C, 53.40; H, 5.99; N, 16.99; F, 1.53%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Cys (Tos)-Gly NH₂ (XIII): m. p. 241°-42°, R_F 0.61; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -66^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found: C, 56.51; H, 6.33; N, 13.85; F, 1.51; C₆₂H₆₂N₁₅O₁₈S₂F requires C, 56.44; H, 6.22; N, 13.73; F, 1.44%).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro(4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (XIV): m. p. 230°-32°, R_F 0.85; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -76^\circ$ (C=1, in D.M.F.), (Found: C, 57.96; H, 6.24; N, 12.41; F, 1.28; C₆₅H₆₆N₁₂O₁₃FS₂, requires C, 58.12; H, 6.40; N, 12.52; F, 1.41%). Amino acid analysis: Cystiene 1.94 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.92 (1 mol), iso-leucine 1.99 (2 mol), glutamic acid 1.00 (1 mol), aspartic acid 0.99 (1 mol), fluoroproline 0.98 (1 mol), and glycine 1.00 (1 mol).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Ser-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Ileu-Gly NH₂ (XV): m. p. 221°-23°, R_F 0.81; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -69^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found: C, 60.35; H, 6.74; N, 12.40; F, 1.63; C₆₅H₆₈N₁₁O₁₃FS₂, requires C, 60.23; H, 6.61; N, 12.23; F, 1.51%). Amino acid analysis: Cystiene 1.96 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.91 (1 mol), iso-leucine 2.01 (2 mol), serine 0.99 (1 mol), aspartic acid 1.02 (1 mol), fluoro-proline 0.98 (1 mol and glycine 1.00 (1 mol).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro(4F)-L-Arg (NO₂)-Gly NH₂ (XVI): m. p. 249°-51°, R_F 0.7; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -77^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found: C, 54.44; H, 5.83; N, 15.51; F, 1.50; C₆₅H₇₅N₁₆O₁₆FS₂ requires C, 54.58; H, 5.94; N, 15.66; F, 1.33%). Amino acid analysis: Cystiene 1.92 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.9 (1 mol), iso-leucine 1.00 (1 mol), glutamic acid 0.99 (1 mol), aspartic acid 1.00 (1 mol), fluoroproline 0.98 (1 mol), arginine 1.00 (1 mol), and glycine 0.99 (1 mol).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro (4F)-L-Lys (Tos)-Gly NH₂ (XVII): m. p. 260-63°, R_F 0.69; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -73^\circ$ (C=1 in D. M. F.). Found: C, 57.03; H, 6.02; N, 12.15; F, 1.33; C₇₂H₉₃N₁₃O₁₆FS₂, requires C, 57.18; H, 6.15; N, 12.04; F, 1.25%). Amino acid analysis: Cystiene 1.98 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.97 (1 mol), iso-leucine 1.0 (1 mol), glutamic acid 0.99 (1 mol), aspartic acid 1.00 (1 mol), fluoroproline 0.98 (1 mol), lysine 1.02 (1 mol), and glycine 0.99 (1 mol).

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